

Hydrogen atom with Darwin potential

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Abstract

We derive exact solutions for the Schrödinger equation for Hydrogen atom with Darwin potential.

1 Introduction

While working on a different problem, we were looking for a formula for energy shift of a strong Darwin potential, where perturbation theory presumably no longer works (or takes too many terms to converge). To our surprise, we found many papers (all wrong) which claim to solve the problem (using Lippman-Schwinger equation) or to calculate perturbation corrections to high order, but they all completely ignore the contribution from continuum states. So we were forced to solve it ourselves.

Darwin potential has been crucial in understanding Hydrogen atom fine structure; there are many misunderstandings about its origin, but that's something we'll discuss elsewhere. Here we'll just concentrate on finding the exact solutions.

To better understand the effects of Darwin potential, we'll start with 1D case where the wave function behaves "properly" and the system can be easily solved, so that we can build some intuitive understanding of the problem. Then we'll expand from there into 3D case.

2 Darwin potential in 1D

Let's take a look at the infinite potential well in one dimension. Schrödinger equation is then

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \psi(x) + V(x)\psi(x) = E\psi(x) \quad (1)$$

where $V(x) = 0$ for $|x| < L$ and infinite otherwise, and the solutions are either even

$$\psi_n = \frac{1}{\sqrt{L}} \cos k_n x, \quad \text{for } n \text{ odd} \quad (2)$$

or odd

$$\psi_n = \frac{1}{\sqrt{L}} \sin k_n x, \quad \text{for } n \text{ even} \quad (3)$$

with

$$k_n = \frac{n\pi}{2L}, \quad E_n = \frac{k_n^2}{2m} = \frac{n^2\pi^2}{8mL^2} \quad (4)$$

So what happens when we throw in a Darwin-type potential¹?

$$V_D(x) = \bar{V}_0 \delta(x) = \frac{V_0}{mL} \delta(x) \quad (5)$$

Well, the solution for $x \neq 0$ by definition has to be a free particle solution (since the potential is zero there), but obviously we expect some sort of effect coming from that δ -function; so for $x > 0$ solution is a superposition of two solutions of the free Schrödinger equation

$$\psi_n^{(+)}(x) = A_n \frac{1}{\sqrt{L}} \cos\left(\frac{\bar{n}\pi x}{2L}\right) + B_n \frac{1}{\sqrt{L}} \sin\left(\frac{\bar{n}\pi x}{2L}\right) \quad (6)$$

where \bar{n} now doesn't have to be an integer. At $x = L$ we have

$$\psi_n^{(+)}(L) = A_n \frac{1}{\sqrt{L}} \cos\left(\frac{\bar{n}\pi}{2}\right) + B_n \frac{1}{\sqrt{L}} \sin\left(\frac{\bar{n}\pi}{2}\right) = 0 \quad (7)$$

which has a solution if and only if

$$A_n = N \cos\frac{\bar{n}\pi\lambda}{2}, \quad B_n = N \sin\frac{\bar{n}\pi\lambda}{2} \quad (8)$$

such that $\bar{n}(1 + \lambda)$ is an odd integer (and N is an overall normalization constant). Similarly for $x < 0$ the solution is given by

$$\psi_n^{(-)}(x) = A'_n \frac{1}{\sqrt{L}} \cos\left(\frac{\bar{n}\pi x}{2L}\right) + B'_n \frac{1}{\sqrt{L}} \sin\left(\frac{\bar{n}\pi x}{2L}\right) \quad (9)$$

and it has to vanish at $x = -L$

$$\psi_n^{(-)}(-L) = A'_n \frac{1}{\sqrt{L}} \cos\left(\frac{\bar{n}\pi}{2}\right) - B'_n \frac{1}{\sqrt{L}} \sin\left(\frac{\bar{n}\pi}{2}\right) = 0 \quad (10)$$

yielding again

$$A'_n = N \cos\frac{\bar{n}\pi\lambda}{2}, \quad B'_n = -N \sin\frac{\bar{n}\pi\lambda}{2} \quad (11)$$

such that $\bar{n}(1 + \lambda)$ is an odd integer. Combining the two, we can write

$$\psi_n^{(\pm)}(x) = A_n \frac{1}{\sqrt{L}} \cos\left(\frac{\bar{n}\pi x}{2L}\right) \pm B_n \frac{1}{\sqrt{L}} \sin\left(\frac{\bar{n}\pi x}{2L}\right) \quad (12)$$

with constants A_n and B_n given by (8). Note that while the total wave function has contribution from both odd and even solutions of Schrödinger equation, change of sign in front of B_n ensures that the total wave function is still even.

To get the second boundary condition (which will determine the value of λ), we integrate the Schrödinger equation around zero

$$\int_{-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} \frac{\partial \psi'(x)}{\partial x} dx - 2m \frac{V_0}{mL} \int_{-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} \delta(x) \psi(x) dx = -2mE \int_{-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} \psi(x) dx \quad (13)$$

and if the wave function is continuous at zero, RHS vanishes, so we get

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \psi'(\epsilon) - \psi'(-\epsilon) = 2m \bar{V}_0 \psi(0) = 2m \frac{V_0}{mL} \psi(0) \quad (14)$$

Figure 1: Shifted wavefunction for attractive (left) and repulsive (right) Darwin potential in 1D infinite square well.

so for odd wave functions which vanish at zero, first derivative is also continuous, and there's no effect (which is hardly surprising since the matrix element of V_D vanishes), but for even ones, first derivative of wave function is discontinuous (the only way the second derivative can be infinite), and it has a value $\pm(V_0/L)\psi(0) = \pm m\bar{V}_0\psi(0)$ on right/left side.

Before we solve this for λ , note that the 1D problem is translationally invariant, so for positive x we can just shift the origin of the wave function to the right (for repulsive potential, or negative V_0) and increase the wave number by just the right amount to get

$$\psi_n^{(+)}(x) = N \cos \frac{n\pi(x + \Delta L)}{2(L + \Delta L)} = N \cos \frac{\bar{n}\pi(x + \lambda L)}{2L} \quad (15)$$

with $\lambda = \Delta L/L$ and $\bar{n} = n/(1 + \lambda)$. Similarly, for negative x we shift the origin to the left, to get

$$\psi_n^{(-)}(x) = N \cos \frac{n\pi(x - \Delta L)}{2(L + \Delta L)} = N \cos \frac{\bar{n}\pi(x - \lambda L)}{2L} \quad (16)$$

where ΔL is some positive number. Combining the two, we get

$$\psi_n^{(\pm)}(x) = N \cos \frac{\bar{n}\pi(x \pm \lambda L)}{2L} \quad (17)$$

which becomes (12) after applying the trigonometric identity $\cos(a \pm b) = \cos a \cos b \mp \sin a \sin b$. Energies are now given by

$$k_n = \frac{\bar{n}\pi}{2L} = \frac{n\pi}{2(L + \Delta L)}, \quad E_n = \frac{k_n^2}{2m} = \frac{\bar{n}^2\pi^2}{8mL^2} = \frac{n^2\pi^2}{8m(L + \Delta L)^2} \quad (18)$$

What has happened here is (for attractive potential, or negative V_0) wavelength became slightly longer (meaning k and E_n became slightly lower), and the phase shifted slightly to the left for positive x and slightly to the right for negative x , so that the wave function is continuous at $x = 0$ but has discontinuous derivative. Value of $\lambda = \Delta L/L$ (which in reality depends on n) is determined by solving the equation

$$\frac{\psi'(0+)}{\psi(0)} = -\frac{\psi'(0-)}{\psi(0)} = \frac{V_0}{L} \quad (19)$$

which can be written as

$$\frac{n\pi\lambda}{2(1 + \lambda)} \tan \frac{n\pi\lambda}{2(1 + \lambda)} = -\lambda V_0 \quad (20)$$

¹ V_0 is dimensionless here, and we're throwing in another dimensionless factor mL purely for convenience.

and can be solved numerically for value $0 < \lambda < 1$. Alternatively, we can note that λ must be a function of V_0 and has to vanish at $V_0 = 0$, meaning $\lambda(0) = 0$. So if we expand the LHS into power series in V_0 and use the notation $\lambda_n = \lambda^{(n)}(0)$, we have (with $N = n\pi/2$)

$$N^2 \lambda_1 = -1 \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{1}{2} N^2 (\lambda_2 - 4\lambda_1^2) = 0 \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{1}{6} N^2 (2(N^2 + 9)\lambda_1^3 - 12\lambda_2\lambda_1 + \lambda_3) = 0 \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{1}{24} N^2 (\lambda_4 - 4(8(N^2 + 3)\lambda_1^4 - 3(N^2 + 9)\lambda_2\lambda_1^2 + 4\lambda_3\lambda_1 + 3\lambda_2^2)) = 0 \quad (24)$$

and so on. This can be solved line by line to get

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda(V_0) = & -\frac{1}{N^2} V_0 + \frac{4}{N^4} \frac{V_0^2}{2!} + \frac{2(N^2 - 15)}{N^6} \frac{V_0^3}{3!} - \frac{48(N^2 - 7)}{N^8} \frac{V_0^4}{4!} - \frac{8(3N^4 - 140N^2 + 630)}{N^{10}} \frac{V_0^5}{5!} \\ & + \frac{64(23N^4 - 450N^2 + 1485)}{N^{12}} \frac{V_0^6}{6!} + \frac{720(N^6 - 98N^4 + 1155N^2 - 3003)}{N^{14}} \frac{V_0^7}{7!} \\ & - \frac{42240(2N^6 - 77N^4 + 637N^2 - 1365)}{N^{16}} \frac{V_0^8}{8!} + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

As we can see, the higher $N = n\pi/2$, the faster this will converge (and will converge the slowest for $n = 1$). Everything we wrote so far works for repulsive potential as well, it's just that ΔL is negative now, so wavelength is shorter and k_n and E_n are higher. Let's expand the energy as a function of V_0 into a power series

$$\begin{aligned} E_n = & \frac{N^2}{2mL^2(1 + \lambda)^2} \\ = & + \frac{N^2}{2mL^2} + \frac{V_0}{mL^2} - \frac{V_0^2}{2mL^2 N^2} - \frac{(N^2 - 3)V_0^3}{3mL^2 N^4} + \frac{(2N^2 - 5)V_0^4}{2mL^2 N^6} + \frac{(3N^4 - 50N^2 + 105)V_0^5}{15mL^2 N^8} \\ & - \frac{(23N^4 - 210N^2 + 378)V_0^6}{18mL^2 N^{10}} + \frac{(-15N^6 + 686N^4 - 4410N^2 + 6930)V_0^7}{105mL^2 N^{12}} \\ & + \frac{11(4N^6 - 84N^4 + 420N^2 - 585)V_0^8}{30mL^2 N^{14}} + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

and compare with perturbation theory. First order is really trivial since matrix elements don't really depend on quantum numbers

$$\langle n | V_D | k \rangle = \int \frac{\cos \frac{n\pi x}{2L}}{\sqrt{L}} \frac{V_0}{mL} \delta(0) \frac{\cos \frac{k\pi x}{2L}}{\sqrt{L}} dx = \frac{V_0}{mL^2} \quad (27)$$

so

$$E_n^{(1)} = \frac{V_0}{mL^2} . \quad (28)$$

Note that since the matrix element of the Darwin potential is just a constant, all the multiple sums in perturbation theory will factorize into product of single sums. Wave function to first order is given by

$$\begin{aligned} |n^{(1)}\rangle = & \sum_{k \neq n} \frac{\langle n | V_D | k \rangle}{E_n - E_k} |k\rangle = \sum_{k \neq n} \frac{\frac{V_0}{mL^2}}{\frac{n^2 \pi^2}{8mL^2} - \frac{k^2 \pi^2}{8mL^2}} \frac{\cos \frac{k\pi x}{2L}}{\sqrt{L}} \\ = & \frac{2V_0}{\pi^2} \left(\frac{\pi(1 - |x|/L)}{n} \frac{\sin \frac{n\pi x}{2L}}{\sqrt{L}} - \frac{1}{n^2} \frac{\cos \frac{n\pi x}{2L}}{\sqrt{L}} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

To the second order we need to evaluate

$$E_n^{(2)} = \sum_{k \neq n} \frac{\langle n | V_D | k \rangle \langle k | V_D | n \rangle}{E_n - E_k} \quad (30)$$

where we have to remember that sum goes over only odd k (and for odd n). For generic n this yields

$$\begin{aligned} E_n^{(2)} &= \left(\frac{V_0}{mL^2} \right)^2 \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\frac{n^2\pi^2}{8mL^2} - \frac{(2k-1)^2\pi^2}{8mL^2}} - \frac{1}{\frac{n^2\pi^2}{8mL^2} - \frac{(n')^2\pi^2}{8mL^2}} \Bigg|_{n=n'} \right\} \\ &= \left(\frac{V_0}{mL^2} \right)^2 \left\{ mL^2 \frac{\tan \frac{n\pi}{2}}{\frac{n\pi}{2}} - \frac{1}{\frac{n^2\pi^2}{8mL^2} - \frac{(n')^2\pi^2}{8mL^2}} \Bigg|_{n=n'} \right\} \\ &= -\frac{2V_0^2}{mL^2\pi^2 n^2} \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

which agrees with V_0^2 term in (26). Third order of perturbation theory

$$\begin{aligned} E_n^{(3)} &= \sum_{k, k' \neq n} \frac{\langle n | V_D | k \rangle \langle k | V_D | k' \rangle \langle k' | V_D | n \rangle}{(E_n - E_k)(E_n - E_{k'})} - \langle n | V_D | n \rangle \sum_{k \neq n} \frac{\langle n | V_D | k \rangle \langle k | V_D | n \rangle}{(E_n - E_k)^2} \\ &= \left(\frac{V_0}{mL^2} \right)^3 \left\{ \left(mL^2 \frac{\tan \frac{n\pi}{2}}{\frac{n\pi}{2}} - \frac{1}{\frac{n^2\pi^2}{8mL^2} - \frac{(n')^2\pi^2}{8mL^2}} \Bigg|_{n=n'} \right)^2 \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \left(\frac{4L^4 m^2 (\pi n - \sin(\pi n))}{\pi^3 n^3 \cos^2 \left(\frac{\pi n}{2} \right)} - \frac{1}{\left(\frac{n^2\pi^2}{8mL^2} - \frac{(n')^2\pi^2}{8mL^2} \right)^2} \Bigg|_{n=n'} \right) \right\} \\ &= -\frac{4(\pi^2 n^2 - 12)V_0^3}{3mL^2 n^4 \pi^4} \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

again agrees with V_0^3 term in (26). We could go on to higher orders here, but we believe we have made our point here that perturbation theory agrees with general solution, so we'll stop here².

Note that the solution which was originally even, gets perturbed into a linear combination of even and odd solution (where odd one has different signs for $x < 0$ and $x > 0$), and the quantum number n gets slightly (well, for small perturbation slightly; for large one maybe not so slightly) shifted up or down, depending on the sign of the perturbation.

2.1 Negative energy state

Note that there can also be a negative energy solution for negative V_0 . For $x > 0$ wave function (with energy $E = -\kappa^2/2m$) can be written as

$$\psi(x) = A_n e^{\kappa x} + B_n e^{-\kappa x} \quad (33)$$

where κ can be determined from boundary conditions. At $x = L$ we must have $\psi = 0$, so wave function can be written as

$$\psi(x) = A (e^{-2\kappa L} e^{\kappa x} - e^{-\kappa x}) \quad (34)$$

²We'll leave it as an exercise for the reader to show that expanding the wave-function (12) in powers of V_0 yields (29) to first order, and higher order WF corrections which we haven't calculated here.

and has a derivative at zero

$$\psi'(x) = A\kappa (e^{\kappa(x-2L)} + e^{-\kappa x}) \rightarrow A\kappa (1 + e^{-2\kappa L}) \quad (35)$$

yielding

$$\frac{\psi'(0)}{\psi(0)} = -\kappa \frac{1 + e^{-2\kappa L}}{1 - e^{-2\kappa L}} = -\frac{\kappa}{\tanh(\kappa L)} = m\bar{V}_0 = \frac{V_0}{L} \quad (36)$$

or

$$\frac{\kappa L}{\tanh(\kappa L)} = -V_0 \quad (37)$$

which will have a real solution for κ if $V_0 < -1$, or in other words, if delta-potential is attractive, and “strong enough” to be binding.

What happens when $L \rightarrow \infty$? Energies of (positive) even states here have shift because of boundary conditions that wave function vanishes at $x = \pm L$. If we remove the infinite well and have a free particle with δ -function potential, odd standing waves will be unaffected and even standing waves will be phase-shifted at zero but their energies will be unchanged (in terms of incoming plane wave, there will be a transmitted and reflected wave, but we’re not going to calculate that here). And as for the negative energy state (which is now the only bound state of the system), prefactor of $e^{\kappa x}$ term is proportional to $e^{-2\kappa L}$ and therefore vanishes, and we are left with only $e^{-\kappa x}$ term, so the boundary condition at $x = 0$ becomes

$$\frac{\psi'(0)}{\psi(0)} = -\kappa = m\bar{V}_0 \quad (38)$$

which now has a solution for any $\bar{V}_0 < 0$.

Bottom line is: for $x \neq 0$ Dirac delta function vanishes, so the solution there is going to be some superposition of solutions of the “free” (meaning without Darwin potential) system. The coefficients of that superposition, and the corresponding energy will be determined by boundary conditions, one of which (at $x = \pm L$) comes from the “free” problem, and the other at $x = 0$ comes from integrating the differential equation around zero (which in 1D case produces a condition on the first derivative of the wave function $\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \psi'(\epsilon)/\psi(\epsilon) \sim V_0$).

3 Darwin potential in 2D and 3D

Naively, we would expect Darwin potential in 2D infinite well to be essentially 1D solution rotated around the vertical axis (2D) or point (3D); that however is not the case. In 2 and 3 dimensions Schrödinger equation is

$$\frac{-1}{2m} \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \right) \psi(\rho) + \frac{V_0}{m} \delta(x)\delta(y)\psi(\rho) = E\psi(\rho) \quad (39)$$

$$\frac{-1}{2m} \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \right) \psi(r) + \frac{V_0}{m^2} \delta(x)\delta(y)\delta(z)\psi(r) = E\psi(r) \quad (40)$$

where we added powers of m in the denominator to make the V_0 dimensionless. Setting $y = z = 0$ doesn’t produce the 1D system, because the 2 and 3 dimensional δ -functions produce additional 1 and 2 infinite factors $\delta(0)$. In polar/spherical coordinates (for $L = 0$) this becomes

$$\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \rho \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \psi(\rho) - \frac{l^2}{\rho^2} \psi(\rho) - 2V_0 \delta^{(2)}(\vec{\rho}) \psi(\rho) = -2mE\psi(\rho) \quad (41)$$

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \psi(r) - \frac{l(l+1)}{r^2} \psi(r) - \frac{2V_0}{m} \delta^{(3)}(\vec{r}) \psi(r) = -2mE\psi(r) \quad (42)$$

and without the Darwin potential, solutions are Bessel functions and Spherical Bessel functions, respectively,

$$\begin{aligned}\psi_{k,l}(\rho) &= (c_1 J_l(k\rho) + c_2 Y_l(k\rho)) = c_1 |k\rangle + c_2 |\tilde{k}\rangle, \\ \psi_{k,l}(r) &= (c_1 j_l(kr) + c_2 y_l(kr)) = c_1 |k\rangle + c_2 |\tilde{k}\rangle\end{aligned}\quad (43)$$

where $k^2 = 2mE$ and we are using the notation $|k\rangle$ to denote solution finite at $r = 0$ and $|\tilde{k}\rangle$ solution that diverges at zero. Since zeros of spherical Bessel functions are very simple, we'll do the analysis here in 3D for brevity (procedure for two dimensions is very similar); once we put this into an infinite potential well, boundary condition at $r = 0$ will require $c_2 = 0$ since Bessel functions of the second kind have poles at zero, and boundary condition at $r = L$ will introduce energy quantization

$$\psi_{k_n,0}(r=L) = 0 \implies k_n = n\pi/L. \quad (44)$$

Since we're only interested in zero angular momentum solutions (because otherwise wave function vanishes at origin and Darwin potential has no effect), our "free" wave functions (radial part) are going to be

$$\psi_n(r) \equiv |n\rangle = \sqrt{\frac{2}{L} \frac{n\pi}{L}} j_0\left(\frac{n\pi}{L} r\right) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{L}} \frac{\sin\left(\frac{n\pi}{L} r\right)}{r} \quad (45)$$

and "free" energies are going to be

$$E_n = \frac{k_n^2}{2m} = \frac{n^2\pi^2}{2mL^2} \quad (46)$$

Now, let's throw in Darwin potential, and try applying the perturbation theory first. To the first order, corrections are $E_n^{(1)} = \langle n | V_D | n \rangle$ which yields³

$$E_n^{(1)} = \frac{V_0}{2\pi m^2 L} \frac{n^2\pi^2}{L^2} \quad (47)$$

but to get the second order, we need to calculate

$$E_n^{(2)} = \sum_{k \neq n} \frac{\langle n | V_D | k \rangle \langle k | V_D | n \rangle}{E_n - E_k} \quad (48)$$

with

$$E_n = \frac{n^2\pi^2}{2mL^2}, \quad \langle n | V_D | k \rangle = \frac{V_0}{2\pi m^2 L} \frac{n\pi}{L} \frac{k\pi}{L} \quad (49)$$

which becomes

$$E_n^{(2)} = \left(\frac{V_0}{2\pi m^2 L}\right)^2 \frac{n^2\pi^2}{L^2} \sum_{k \neq n} \frac{\frac{k^2\pi^2}{L^2}}{\frac{n^2\pi^2}{2mL^2} - \frac{k^2\pi^2}{2mL^2}} = 2m \left(\frac{V_0}{2\pi m^2 L}\right)^2 \frac{n^2\pi^2}{L^2} \sum_{k \neq n} \frac{k^2}{n^2 - k^2} \quad (50)$$

which diverges. To understand better what's going on, let's calculate wave function corrections too; to the first order, we have

$$|n^{(1)}\rangle = \sum_{k \neq n} \frac{\langle n | V_D | k \rangle}{E_n - E_k} |k\rangle \quad (51)$$

³If you haven't figured it out, an extra $1/4\pi$ factor comes from angular part of wave function

yielding

$$|n^{(1)}\rangle = \frac{V_0}{\pi m L} \sum_{k \neq n} \frac{nk}{n^2 - k^2} |k\rangle \quad (52)$$

which can actually be summed up for spherical Bessel functions to yield

$$\begin{aligned} |n^{(1)}\rangle &= \frac{V_0}{4\pi m L} \sqrt{\frac{2}{L}} \left(\frac{\sin \frac{n\pi r}{L}}{r} - 2n\pi \left(1 - \frac{|r|}{L}\right) \frac{\cos \frac{n\pi r}{L}}{r} \right) \\ &= \frac{V_0}{4\pi m L} \left(|n\rangle - 2n\pi \left(1 - \frac{|r|}{L}\right) |\tilde{n}\rangle \right) \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

which (as we can see) picks up a contribution of the other “irregular” solution of the Bessel spherical differential equation that’s infinite at $r = 0$, and since the n^{th} order energy correction can be written as

$$E_n^{(N)} = \langle n^{(0)} | V | n^{(N-1)} \rangle \quad (54)$$

we can see that the second order contribution to energy diverges because the first order correction of the wavefunction is infinite at $r = 0$. While this may sound like we’re doing something wrong at first, we’re not; we will show soon that we *must* have that irregular WF contribution since that’s the only way to get the δ -function.

Let’s try solving the problem analytically. Like in $1D$, the solution is going to be a superposition of the two solutions to the free Schrödinger equation, $j_0(kr)$ and $y_0(kr)$ with $k = \bar{n}\pi/L$ where now \bar{n} no longer needs to be an integer. Requiring that the wave function vanishes at $r = L$ produces the requirement like (8)

$$A_n = \cos \bar{n}\pi\lambda, \quad B_n = \sin \bar{n}\pi\lambda \quad (55)$$

such that $\bar{n}(1 + \lambda)$ is an integer, yielding the overall solution⁴

$$\psi^\pm(r) = N \frac{\sin(n\pi(\lambda + r/L))}{r} = N \left(\cos(\bar{n}\pi\lambda) \frac{\sin \frac{\bar{n}\pi r}{L}}{r} \pm \sin(\bar{n}\pi\lambda) \frac{\cos \frac{\bar{n}\pi r}{L}}{r} \right) \quad (56)$$

where N is the overall normalization constant. Now, to get the boundary condition at $r = 0$, we need to integrate the Schrödinger equation over $r = 0$; we can do this either by integrating the equation over a sphere of radius ϵ which then goes to zero, or by multiplying the equation by r^2 and integrating over r from $-\epsilon$ to ϵ . Since region $r < 0$ is non-physical, we’ll stick to the first approach (although both yield the same result).

The Darwin potential is proportional to $\delta^{(3)}(r)$, which is usually quoted in textbooks as

$$\delta^{(3)}(r) = \frac{\delta(r)}{2\pi r^2} \quad (57)$$

and needless to say, this doesn’t lead anywhere, as we already saw in the perturbation theory example. So what is the correct representation of δ -function? Well, the reason why we got that delta function in the first place was because potential in the momentum space

$$V(p, q) \sim \lim_{\mu \rightarrow 0} \frac{(\vec{p} - \vec{q})^2}{(\vec{p} - \vec{q})^2 + \mu^2} \quad (58)$$

⁴Region $r < 0$ is actually not a physical region, so one may wonder why would we have to require that the wave function vanishes at $r = -L$? The best answer we can come up with is “symmetry”, but one doesn’t have to look at $r < 0$ region at all to derive the results here.

is proportional to a constant, and the Fourier transform of a constant is a δ -function. But since the problem is spherically symmetric, let's do this in spherical coordinates:

$$\begin{aligned} V(r) &= \frac{V_0/m^2}{(2\pi)^3} \int e^{-i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}} d^3k = \frac{V_0/m^2}{(2\pi)^3} \int_0^\infty \int_{-1}^1 e^{-ikr \cos \theta} 2\pi k^2 d \cos \theta dk \\ &= \frac{V_0/m^2}{(2\pi)^2} \int_0^\infty \frac{e^{ikr} - e^{-ikr}}{ikr} k^2 dk = \lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \frac{V_0/m^2}{(2\pi)^2 i r} \int_0^\infty (e^{ik(r+i\sigma)} - e^{-ik(r-i\sigma)}) k dk \end{aligned} \quad (59)$$

where in the last step we added small imaginary part σ to r to make integrals converge. Last integral can easily be evaluated using partial integration, to get

$$V(r) = \lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \frac{V_0/m^2}{(2\pi)^2 i r} \left(\frac{1}{(r+i\sigma)^2} - \frac{1}{(r-i\sigma)^2} \right) = \lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \frac{V_0/m^2}{\pi^2} \frac{\sigma}{(r^2 + \sigma^2)^2} \quad (60)$$

One can easily see that

$$\int \frac{1}{\pi^2} \frac{\sigma}{(r^2 + \sigma^2)^2} d^3r = 1 \quad (61)$$

for all $\sigma > 0$, so in the limit $\sigma \rightarrow 0$ it's really is a representation of $\delta^{(3)}(\vec{r})$. If we now integrate the Schrödinger equation over a sphere of radius ϵ (and then let $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$) to get

$$\int \nabla^2 \psi(r) d^3r - \frac{2V_0}{m\pi^2} \int_0^\epsilon \frac{\sigma}{(r^2 + \sigma^2)^2} \psi(r) 4\pi r^2 dr = k_n^2 \int_0^\epsilon \psi(r) 4\pi r^2 dr \quad (62)$$

and since we'll be integrating over very narrow area around zero, wave function can be approximated as

$$\psi^\pm(r) \approx N k_n \left(A_n + \frac{B_n}{k_n r} \right), \quad (63)$$

To evaluate the first term on the LHS we note that

$$\nabla^2 \psi(r) \approx \nabla^2 N \left(A_n + \frac{B_n}{k_n r} \right) = N B_n (-4\pi \delta^{(3)}(r)) \quad (64)$$

yielding

$$\int \nabla^2 \psi(r) d^3r = -4\pi N B_n \quad (65)$$

Or alternatively, if we use the Gauss theorem to write

$$\begin{aligned} \int \nabla \cdot (\nabla \psi) d^3r &= \int (\nabla \psi) \cdot d\vec{S} = \int \left(\hat{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \psi(r) \right) \cdot \hat{r} r^2 d\Omega = 4\pi \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \psi(r) \right) \Big|_{r=\epsilon} \\ &= 4\pi N \left\{ \cos \left(\frac{\pi n \epsilon}{L} \right) \left(\frac{A_n (\pi n \epsilon)}{L} - B_n \right) - \sin \left(\frac{\pi n \epsilon}{L} \right) \left(A_n + \frac{B_n (\pi n \epsilon)}{L} \right) \right\} \\ &= -4\pi N B_n + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2) \end{aligned} \quad (66)$$

we get the same result. RHS can be integrated into

$$k_n^2 \int_0^\epsilon \psi(r) 4\pi r^2 dr = 2\pi \left(B_n k_n^2 \epsilon^2 + \frac{2}{3} A_n \epsilon^3 k_n^3 - \frac{1}{4} B_n k_n^4 \epsilon^4 + \dots \right) \quad (67)$$

which vanishes in the $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$ limit⁵. Finally, the Darwin term is the most interesting one

$$-\frac{2V_0}{m} \int_0^\epsilon \frac{1}{\pi^2 (r^2 + \sigma^2)^2} \frac{\sigma}{r} \psi(r) 4\pi r^2 dr = -\frac{2V_0}{m} N \int_0^\epsilon \frac{1}{\pi^2 (r^2 + \sigma^2)^2} \left(k_n A_n + \frac{B_n}{r} \right) r^2 dr \quad (68)$$

Here we have to be careful; in the first term (proportional to A_n) we can just take the $\sigma \rightarrow 0$ limit to get the δ function and integrate over ϵ to get

$$-\frac{2V_0}{m} \int_0^\epsilon \frac{1}{\pi^2 (r^2 + \sigma^2)^2} \frac{\sigma}{r} k_n A_n 4\pi r^2 dr = -\frac{2V_0}{m} \int_0^\epsilon \delta^{(3)}(\vec{r}) k_n A_n d^3 r = -\frac{2V_0}{m} k_n A_n \quad (69)$$

Second term is a bit trickier. Integrating it yields the result

$$\int_0^\epsilon \frac{1}{\pi^2 (r^2 + \sigma^2)^2} \left(\frac{B_n}{r} \right) 4\pi r^2 dr = \frac{2}{\pi} \frac{B_n \epsilon^2}{\sigma(\sigma^2 + \epsilon^2)}. \quad (70)$$

which depends on the order which of the variables ϵ and σ we set to zero first. Since our δ -function potential is really the limit $\sigma \rightarrow 0$ of (60), as long as $\sigma > 0$ is finite, this term vanishes in the $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$. This leads to somewhat surprising result that

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_0^\epsilon \frac{\delta^{(3)}(\vec{r})}{r} 4\pi r^2 dr = 0 \quad (71)$$

which seems somewhat counter-intuitive at first. The only “problem” with this approach is that letting $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$ first while keeping σ constant leads to the conclusion that the first term (proportional to A_n) also vanishes, so it seems like we are cheating here by choosing how we let ϵ and σ to zero essentially arbitrarily (or as mean people would say, “to get the result we want”).

Other choice of letting $\sigma \rightarrow 0$ first (while keeping ϵ constant is same as letting $\epsilon \rightarrow \infty$) and leads to infinite result

$$\int_0^\epsilon \frac{1}{\pi^2 (r^2 + \sigma^2)^2} \left(\frac{B_n}{r} \right) 4\pi r^2 dr \rightarrow \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{\pi^2 (r^2 + \sigma^2)^2} \left(\frac{B_n}{r} \right) 4\pi r^2 dr = \frac{2}{\pi\sigma} B_n. \quad (72)$$

Third choice is to let them to to zero simultaneously, by having

$$\epsilon = \sqrt{\frac{C\pi^2}{m}} \sigma^\alpha \quad (73)$$

⁵If we add up those two terms, the result is actually $-B_n$ and doesn't depend on ϵ at all, because away from zero, $B_n \cos(\bar{n}\pi r/L)/r$ satisfies the “free” equation, so the integrand identically vanishes for $r > 0$.

with C some proportionality constant; in this case the result is either zero (for $\alpha > 3/2$), infinite (for $\alpha < 3/2$) or constant (for $\alpha = 3/2$)

$$\frac{2}{\pi} \frac{B_n \epsilon^2}{\sigma(\sigma^2 + \epsilon^2)} = \frac{B_n 2\pi C/m}{(1 + C\pi^2\sigma/m)} \rightarrow 2\pi C B_n/m. \quad (74)$$

This is actually the most general case, since $C = 0$ covers the first scenario where ϵ goes to zero while σ is constant, and $C = m/(\pi^2\sigma) \rightarrow \infty$ covers the case where σ goes to zero while ϵ is constant, so we'll keep C for now and see how it affects the solution. We are left with

$$-4\pi B_n - \frac{2V_0}{m}(k_n A_n + 2\pi C B_n/m) = 0 \implies \sin \bar{n}\pi\lambda(1 + V_0 C) + \frac{V_0}{2mL}\bar{n} \cos \bar{n}\pi\lambda = 0 \quad (75)$$

which can again be solved either numerically, or by expanding into power series like the 1D case (using $N = n\pi$ and $M = 1/(2\pi mL)$)

$$\lambda_1 = -M \quad (76)$$

$$2\lambda_1(C - \lambda_1 - M) + \lambda_2 = 0 \quad (77)$$

$$3\lambda_2(C - 2\lambda_1 - M) - \lambda_1^2(6C + 3M(N^2 - 2) + \lambda_1(N^2 - 6)) + \lambda_3 = 0 \quad (78)$$

$$4\lambda_3(C - 2\lambda_1 - M) + 4\lambda_1^3(3\lambda_1(N^2 - 2) - (N^2(C - 9M)) + 6(C - M)) - 6\lambda_2\lambda_1(4C + 2M(N^2 - 2) + \lambda_1(N^2 - 6)) - 6\lambda_2^2 + \lambda_4 = 0 \quad (79)$$

which can then be solved line by line

$$\lambda_1 = -M = -\frac{1}{2\pi mL} \quad (80)$$

$$\lambda_2 = 2CM = \frac{C}{mL\pi} \quad (81)$$

$$\lambda_3 = 2M^3N^2 - 6C^2M = \frac{n^2 - 12C^2L^2m^2}{4\pi m^3L^3} \quad (82)$$

$$\lambda_4 = 16M^4N^2 + 24C^3M - 24M^3CN^2 = \frac{n^2 + 3CLm(4C^2m^2L^2 - n^2)\pi}{m^4L^4\pi^2} \quad (83)$$

and so on. Plugging these back into the expression for energy, we get

$$E = \frac{n^2\pi^2}{2mL^2(1 + \lambda)^2} = \frac{\pi^2 n^2}{2L^2 m} + \frac{n^2\pi}{2m^2 L^3} V_0 + \frac{(3m - 4CL\pi)n^2}{8m^4 L^4} V_0^2 - \frac{n^2(m^2(\pi^2 n^2 - 6) - 18CLm\pi + 12C^2L^2\pi^2)}{24\pi m^6 L^5} V_0^3 + \frac{n^2(5m^3 n^2(3 - 2\pi^2 n^2) + 12CL\pi(9CLm\pi - 4C^2L^2\pi^2 + m^2(-6 + n^2\pi^2)))}{96\pi^2 m^8 L^6} V_0^4 + \dots \quad (84)$$

First thing to notice is that this diverges for $C \rightarrow \infty$; however, if we assume that V_0 is small “enough” that tangens in equation (75) can be approximated $\tan x \approx x$, then we can solve it to get

$$\lambda \approx -\frac{MV_0}{1 + CV} \quad (85)$$

which goes to zero for infinite C , which would imply that Darwin potential has no effect; since we believe that Darwin potential *does* have real measurable effects, we will exclude that option.

Second thing we can see is that the lowest term agrees with first order perturbation theory result, regardless of value of C , so first order result in itself isn't going to tell us much about C . What about higher orders? Well, the sum in (50) is still infinite, but we can use the formula (53) combined with (54) to evaluate 2nd order:

$$\begin{aligned} E_n^{(2)} &= \int \langle n | \frac{V_0}{m^2 \pi^2} \frac{\sigma}{(r^2 + \sigma^2)^2} \frac{V_0}{4\pi m L} \left(|n\rangle - 2n\pi \left(1 - \frac{r}{L}\right) |\tilde{n}\rangle \right) r^2 dr \\ &= \frac{V_0^2}{4\pi m^3 L} \left(\frac{n^2 \pi}{2L^3} + \frac{2n\pi}{L} \frac{n}{2L^2} - 2n\pi \int \langle n | \frac{1}{\pi^2} \frac{\sigma}{(r^2 + \sigma^2)^2} |\tilde{n}\rangle r^2 dr \right) \end{aligned} \quad (86)$$

Last integral is equals

$$\int \langle n | \frac{1}{\pi^2} \frac{\sigma}{(r^2 + \sigma^2)^2} |\tilde{n}\rangle r^2 dr = \frac{2}{L} \frac{n\pi}{L} \int \frac{1}{\pi^2} \frac{\sigma}{(r^2 + \sigma^2)^2} \frac{1}{r} r^2 dr = \frac{2}{L} \frac{n\pi}{L} \frac{1}{2\pi^2 \sigma} = \frac{n}{\pi L^2 \sigma} \quad (87)$$

and is infinite (in the $\sigma \rightarrow 0$ limit), but the second order correction can formally be written as

$$E_n^{(2)} = \frac{n^2 V_0^2}{8m^3 L^4} \left(3 - \frac{4L}{\pi \sigma} \right) \quad (88)$$

which matches second term in (84) if we use $C = m/(\pi^2 \sigma)$. Perhaps we are missing something important here, but it seems to us that C should be zero, although the argument for that is not exactly rock-solid, since the choice how to let σ and ϵ to zero seems pretty arbitrary to us. But that then leads to the conclusion that the integral of $\delta^{(3)}(\vec{r})/r$ must vanish, which perhaps *might* be true in some distribution sense, but we sure don't know how to prove it.

3.1 Negative energy state

Now, as we saw in 1D case, there can also be a negative energy state, which can be written either in terms of either hyperbolic or exponential functions

$$\psi(r) = A \frac{\sinh \kappa r}{r} + B \frac{\cosh \kappa r}{r} \quad (89)$$

where energy is now

$$E = -\frac{\kappa^2}{2m}. \quad (90)$$

Boundary condition that wave function vanishes at $r = L$ lead to

$$A = N \cosh(\kappa L), \quad B = -N \sinh(\kappa L) \quad (91)$$

giving us the wave function

$$\psi = N \cosh \kappa L \frac{\sinh \kappa r}{r} - N \sinh \kappa L \frac{\cosh \kappa r}{r} = N \frac{\sinh(\kappa(r - L))}{r} \quad (92)$$

To get the κ , we have to again integrate the Schrödinger equation over a sphere of radius ϵ and then let $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$. Everything is the same as for positive energy states, and we're left with the equation

$$-4\pi B_n - \frac{2V_0}{m} (\kappa A_n + 2\pi C B_n/m) = 0 \implies \sinh \kappa L (1 + V_0 C) + \frac{V_0}{2\pi m L} \kappa L \cosh \kappa L = 0 \quad (93)$$

Note that the equation

$$\tanh(\kappa L) = -\frac{V_0/(2m\pi L)}{1 + V_0 C} \kappa L \quad (94)$$

has a single solution, only if

$$-\frac{V_0/(2m\pi L)}{1 + V_0 C} < 1 \quad (95)$$

What happens if we let $L \rightarrow \infty$? Left hand side becomes one, and we are left with

$$-\frac{V_0/(2m\pi)}{1 + V_0 C} \kappa = 1 \implies \kappa = (1 - |V_0|C) \frac{2m\pi}{|V_0|} \quad (96)$$

which for $C = 0$ leads to energy

$$E = -\frac{2m\pi^2}{V_0^2} \quad (97)$$

This is contradictory to results derived from having a finite depth potential well

$$V(r) = \begin{cases} -V_0/R & \text{for } r < R \\ 0 & \text{for } r > R \end{cases} \quad (98)$$

which conclude that there is an infinite number of bound states, with (negative) infinite energy each. The reason for that is because wave function inside the well has to be proportional to $\sin(kr)/r$, so at zero it's finite and has zero first derivative, but at the edge of the well $r = R$ it has to be matched to $e^{-\kappa r}/r$ which is infinite (in the $R = 0$ limit) and has (negative) infinite first derivative, which is impossible to do.

4 Hydrogen atom with Darwin potential

4.1 Coulomb potential...

Before we start, let's re-derive the Coulomb/Yukawa potential in coordinate space. In momentum space the potential is derived from 1-photon exchange, and has the form

$$V(p, q) = \frac{e^2}{(\vec{p} - \vec{q})^2 + \mu^2} \quad (99)$$

so we need to calculate the inverse Fourier transform back into coordinate space

$$\begin{aligned} V(r) &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \int \frac{e^2}{q^2 + \mu^2} e^{i\vec{q}\cdot\vec{r}} d^3q = \frac{e^2}{(2\pi)^3} \int_0^\infty \int_{-1}^1 \frac{e^{iqr \cos \theta}}{q^2 + \mu^2} 2\pi d \cos \theta q^2 dq \\ &= \frac{e^2}{(2\pi)^2} \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{(q + i\mu)(q - i\mu)} \frac{e^{iqr} - e^{-iqr}}{ir} q dq . \end{aligned} \quad (100)$$

In the second term (proportional to e^{-iqr} we can change the variables $q \rightarrow -q$, which then becomes the same as first term, but from $-\infty$ to 0, so adding them up we get

$$V(r) = \frac{e^2}{ir(2\pi)^2} \int_{-\infty}^\infty \frac{e^{iqr}}{(q + i\mu)(q - i\mu)} q dq \quad (101)$$

It's customary to say that since $r > 0$, we can use the residue theorem by closing the loop in the upper half of the plane to get

$$V(r) = \frac{e^2}{ir(2\pi)^2} (2\pi i) \operatorname{Res} \frac{e^{iqr}}{(q+i\mu)(q-i\mu)} q \Big|_{q=i\mu} = \frac{e^2}{ir(2\pi)^2} \pi i e^{-\mu r} = \frac{\alpha e^{-\mu r}}{r} \quad (102)$$

However, just because *physically* $r < 0$ doesn't make any sense, *mathematically* we can evaluate (101) for $r < 0$ just fine; in which case we need to close the loop in the lower part of the complex q plane (and add a minus one factor because the loop integral is now in the clockwise direction instead of counter-clockwise) to get

$$V(r) = \frac{e^2}{ir(2\pi)^2} (-2\pi i) \operatorname{Res} \frac{e^{iqr}}{(q+i\mu)(q-i\mu)} q \Big|_{q=-i\mu} = \frac{e^2}{ir(2\pi)^2} (-\pi i) e^{\mu r} = \frac{\alpha e^{\mu r}}{-r} . \quad (103)$$

The two results can jointly be written as

$$V(r) = \alpha \frac{e^{-\mu|r|}}{|r|} . \quad (104)$$

which in the $\mu \rightarrow 0$ limit leads to the "usual" definition of Coulomb potential, extended into the (un-physical) $r < 0$ region.

4.2 ... and it's regular solutions...

Plugging that potential into the Schrödinger equation, we get the differential equation for Hydrogen atom (for $r > 0$),

$$-\frac{\kappa}{2m} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial r^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial r} - \frac{l(l+1)}{r^2} \psi \right] - \frac{\alpha}{r} \psi = E \psi \quad (105)$$

where $\kappa = 1$ for Hydrogen and $\kappa = 2$ for Positronium (or quarkonium) states, which can be written as

$$\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial r^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial r} - \frac{l(l+1)}{r^2} \psi + \frac{2}{ra_0} \psi = k^2 \psi \quad (106)$$

with $a_0 = \kappa/(m\alpha)$ and $k = \sqrt{-2mE/\kappa}$. If we now substitute $\psi(r) = e^{-kr} r^l f(2kr)$, we get

$$2kr f''(2kr) + (2l+2-2kr) f'(2kr) - \left(1+l - \frac{1}{ka_0} \right) f(2kr) = 0 \quad (107)$$

which is the Hypergeometric differential equation with the solution being Hypergeometric function

$$f(2kr) = {}_1F_1\left(1+l - \frac{1}{ka_0}, 2l+2, 2kr\right) \quad (108)$$

which is also known as Kummer's function. For bound state solutions energies E are negative and k is real and positive yielding the solutions

$$\psi(r) = e^{\mp kr} (kr)^l {}_1F_1\left(1+l \mp \frac{1}{ka_0}, 2(1+l), \pm 2kr\right) . \quad (109)$$

For real k the Hypergeometric function will grow like exponential function, so the only normalizable (physical) solution is one with the negative sign

$$\psi(r) = e^{-kr} (kr)^l {}_1F_1 \left(1 + l - \frac{1}{ka_0}, 2(1 + l), 2kr \right), \quad (110)$$

and only if the first parameter happens to be non-positive integer

$$1 + l - \frac{1}{ka_0} = -(n - l - 1) \implies E = -\frac{\kappa m(\alpha/\kappa)^2}{2n^2} = -\frac{\kappa}{2m a_n^2} \quad (111)$$

in which case it terminates and becomes a polynomial, yielding the usual (associated) Laguerre polynomials. For imaginary k , the same formula holds, but let's now make a change $k \rightarrow ik$ to make k real and positive again:

$$\psi(r) = e^{\mp ikr} (ikr)^l {}_1F_1 \left(1 + l \mp \frac{1}{ika_0}, 2(1 + l), \pm 2ikr \right). \quad (112)$$

These solutions are actually real (and same) and it's customary to keep the positive sign in the exponential term

$$\psi(r) = e^{+ikr} (ikr)^l {}_1F_1 \left(1 + l + \frac{1}{ika_0}, 2(1 + l), -2ikr \right). \quad (113)$$

to make the solution proportional⁶ to (radial) Coulomb Wave Functions [8, 9]

$$\psi_{k,l}(r) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \frac{F_l(-\frac{1}{ka_0}, kr)}{kr} \quad (114)$$

where F is known as the (real) “regular” Coulomb Wave Function

$$F_l(\eta, \rho) = \frac{e^{-\frac{\pi\eta}{2}} 2^l \sqrt{\Gamma(1 + l + i\eta) \Gamma(1 + l - i\eta)}}{\Gamma(2l + 2)} e^{i\rho} \rho^{l+1} {}_1F_1(1 + l + i\eta, 2(l + 1), -2i\rho). \quad (115)$$

Normalizing these wave function requires calculating the overlap of two wave functions (which we'll skip doing here), yielding the result

$$\psi_{n,l}(r) = \mathcal{N}_{n,l} e^{-r/(na_0)} \left(\frac{2r}{na_0} \right)^l {}_1F_1 \left(1 + l - n, 2l + l, \frac{2r}{na_0} \right) \quad (116)$$

$$\psi_{k,l}(r) = \mathcal{N}_{k,l} k e^{ikr} (2kr)^l {}_1F_1 \left(1 + l + \frac{1}{ika_0}, 2l + 2, -2ikr \right). \quad (117)$$

with normalization constants

$$\mathcal{N}_{n,l} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{a_0^3} \frac{\Gamma(n + l + 1)}{\Gamma(n - l)} \frac{2}{n^2 \Gamma(2l + 2)}} \quad (118)$$

$$\mathcal{N}_{k,l} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \sqrt{\Gamma \left(1 + l + \frac{1}{ika_0} \right) \Gamma \left(1 + l - \frac{1}{ika_0} \right) \frac{e^{\frac{\pi}{2|ka_0|}}}{\Gamma(2l + 2)}} \quad (119)$$

⁶Factor $\sqrt{2/\pi}$ comes from the fact that regular Coulomb wave functions are normalized to $\frac{\pi}{2} \delta(k - k')$

normalized as

$$\int_0^{\infty} \psi_{n,l}^*(r) \psi_{n',l}(r) r^2 dr = \delta_{n,n'} \quad (120)$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} \psi_{k,l}^*(r) \psi_{k',l}(r) r^2 dr = \delta(k - k') \quad (121)$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} \psi_{n,l}^*(r) \psi_{k,l}(r) r^2 dr = 0 \quad (122)$$

While the continuum and bound state functions are related by substitution $k \rightarrow i/n$ or $n \rightarrow i/k$, their normalization factors aren't, and in fact they diverge if the substitution is made.

4.3 ... as well as irregular solutions...

This is (for bound states at least) standard textbook material; the “irregular” solutions, not so much. Second linearly independent solution for Hydrogen atom will be proportional to the second linearly independent solution to the hypergeometric equation; if ${}_1F_1(a, c, x)$ is one solution of the hypergeometric equation, for non-integer c , second linearly independent solution⁷ will be $x^{1-c} {}_1F_1(a + 1 - c, 2 - c, x)$. Unfortunately for us, we need the solution where c is an integer, which is usually written in terms of Tricomi function defined as

$$U(a, c, x) = \frac{\Gamma(1-c)}{\Gamma(a+1-c)} {}_1F_1(a, c, x) + \frac{\Gamma(c-1)}{\Gamma(a)} x^{1-c} {}_1F_1(a+1-c, 2-c, x). \quad (123)$$

which despite it's appearance is properly defined (by continuity) even for integer c , and is also a solution to the Hypergeometric differential equation. When c is an integer, both $\Gamma(1-c)$ and ${}_1F_1(a+1-c, 2-c, x)$ have a pole, so we set $c = 1 + n + \epsilon$ in formula (123) and then take a limit $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$. Two poles cancel exactly and we are left with

$$U(a, 1+n, z) = \frac{\Gamma(n)}{\Gamma(a)} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(a-n)_k}{(1-n)_k} \frac{z^{k-n}}{k!} + \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{\Gamma(1+n)\Gamma(a-n)} \left\{ {}_1F_1(a, 1+n, z) \log(z) + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_k}{(1+n)_k} (\psi(a+k) - \psi(1+n+k) - \psi(1+k)) \frac{z^k}{k!} \right\} \quad (124)$$

For continuum states one typically usually uses “irregular” Coulomb wave function $G_l(\eta, x)/r$, which is defined as real part of complex Coulomb wave function

$$\begin{aligned} H_l^{\pm}(\eta, x) &= G_l(\eta, x) \pm iF_l(\eta, x) \\ &= \pm i e^{\eta\pi/2} \left(\frac{\Gamma(1+l+i\eta)}{\Gamma(1+l-i\eta)} \right)^{\pm \frac{1}{2}} e^{\pm ix} (-2x)^{l+1} U(1+l \pm i\eta, 2l+2, \mp 2ix) \end{aligned} \quad (125)$$

that represent incoming/outgoing waves. In the limit $r \rightarrow \infty$ we have

$$H^{\pm} \rightarrow e^{\pm i\theta_l}, \quad F_l \rightarrow \sin \theta_l, \quad \text{and} \quad G_l \rightarrow \cos \theta_l \quad (126)$$

⁷For the detailed discussion we recommend reading [5] section on Confluent hypergeometric function.

with

$$\theta_l = x - \eta \log(2x) - l\pi/2 + \sigma_l, \quad \sigma_l = \arg \Gamma(1 + l + i\eta) = -i \log \sqrt{\frac{\Gamma(1 + l + i\eta)}{\Gamma(1 + l - i\eta)}}. \quad (127)$$

while in the limit $r \rightarrow 0$ we have

$$F_l \rightarrow r^l, \quad \text{and} \quad G_l \rightarrow r^{-(l+1)} \quad (128)$$

which is why F_l is called “regular” and G_l “irregular” solution⁸. In the limit $\alpha \rightarrow 0$ (or $a_0 \rightarrow \infty$), regular Coulomb wave functions (positive energy solutions) become proportional to spherical Bessel functions

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{F_l(0, kr)}{kr} &= j_l(kr) = \frac{\Gamma(l+1)}{\Gamma(2l+2)} e^{ikr} (2kr)^l {}_1F_1(1+l, 2(1+l), -2ikr) \\ \frac{G_l(0, kr)}{kr} &= -y_l(kr), \quad \frac{H_+(0, kr)}{kr} = ih_l^{(1)}(kr), \quad \frac{H_-(0, kr)}{kr} = -ih_l^{(2)}(kr) \end{aligned} \quad (129)$$

so regular and irregular Coulomb wave function solutions are analog to spherical Bessel functions solution in the free problem.

Bound state solutions in general behave like continuum solutions imaginary η (meaning with k replaced by i/\bar{n}), and so for large r and general \bar{n} they will behave like

$$H^\pm \rightarrow e^{\mp r/\bar{n}}, \quad F_l \rightarrow \sinh(r/\bar{n}), \quad \text{and} \quad G_l \rightarrow \cosh(r/\bar{n}) \quad (130)$$

but for integer n “regular” solution F_l actually behaves like $e^{-r/n}$ because the hypergeometric function terminates after a finite number of terms and becomes a polynomial instead of exponential, so it’s customary to keep that one. The other “irregular” solution that corresponds to $G_l(\eta, \rho)$ behaves like $\cosh(r/\bar{n})$, so bound state would have to be a linear combination of G_l and F_l where $e^{r/\bar{n}}$ parts cancel exactly; which happens to be $H^+(\eta, \rho)$ with imaginary η , so we’ll just use that one from the start

$$\tilde{\psi}(r) = e^{-kr} r^l U\left(1+l - \frac{1}{ka_0}, 2(1+l), 2kr\right) \quad (131)$$

which at $r = 0$ has both a pole and a logarithmic singularity (unless $1+l - 1/(ka_0) = 1+l - n$ is a negative integer, in which case it’s actually proportional to the regular solution). Overlap of these two wave functions

$$\int \tilde{\psi}_l^*(r) \tilde{\psi}_l(r) d^3r = \int_0^\infty e^{-2r/\bar{n}} r^{2l+2} U(1+l - \bar{n}, 2(1+l), 2r/\bar{n})^2 dr \quad (132)$$

will generally diverge because the integrand behaves like r^{-2l} around zero, but thankfully we only need the $l = 0$ solution here, which converges

$$\begin{aligned} \int \tilde{\psi}_0^*(r) \tilde{\psi}_0(r) d^3r &= \int_0^\infty e^{-2r/\bar{n}} U(1 - \bar{n}, 2, 2r/\bar{n})^2 r^2 dr \\ &= \Gamma(n+1)^2 \left(\frac{n^3}{4} - \frac{n \sin^2(\pi n)}{8 \pi^2} (1 - 2n + 2n^2 \psi^{(1)}(n+1)) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (133)$$

⁸ G_l also has logarithmic terms, but we won’t dwell into details here.

which yields the normalized wave function for $l = 0$

$$\psi(r) = \mathcal{N}_n e^{-r/(\bar{n}a_0)} U(1 - \bar{n}, 2, 2r/(\bar{n}a_0)), \quad (134)$$

with

$$\mathcal{N}_n = \frac{2}{\Gamma(n+1)(na_0)^{3/2}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{\sin^2(\pi n)}{2\pi^2 n^2} (1 - 2n + 2n^2 \psi^{(1)}(n+1))}} \quad (135)$$

Note that for integer $\bar{n} = n$, regular and irregular solutions are proportional to each other because for integer l and n and $n > l$

$$U(1+l-n, 2l+2, z) = (-1)^{1+l-n} \frac{\Gamma(1+l+n)}{\Gamma(2l+2)} {}_1F_1(1+l-n, 2l+2, z) \quad (136)$$

4.4 Darwin potential

Before we start, a short digression: let's multiply the Schrödinger equation for Hydrogen atom (with the potential properly extended to $r < 0$ region) with r^2 and integrate from $-\epsilon$ to ϵ

$$\int_{-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} [r^2 \psi'(r)] dr = -2m \int_{-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} \alpha |r| \psi(r) dr - 2mE \int_{-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} r^2 \psi(r) dr \quad (137)$$

If the wave function is continuous at zero, we have

$$\epsilon^2(\psi'(\epsilon) - \psi'(-\epsilon)) = -2m\alpha [\epsilon^2 \psi(0) + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^3)] - 2mE \left[\frac{\epsilon^3}{3} \psi(0) + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^4) \right] \quad (138)$$

which after dividing by ϵ^2 and then letting $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$ leads to

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} (\psi'(\epsilon) - \psi'(-\epsilon)) = -2m\alpha \psi(0) = -\frac{2}{a_0} \psi(0) \quad (139)$$

which (due to symmetry) means that the derivative of the logarithm of the wave function at zero has to have values

$$\left. \frac{\partial \log \psi(r)}{\partial r} \right|_{r=0^\pm} = \frac{\psi'(0^\pm)}{\psi(0)} = \pm \frac{1}{a_0} \quad (140)$$

on the left/right side of $r = 0$. It's easy to see that both bound state and continuum solutions satisfy this.

Note that this is essentially the same as boundary condition for Darwin potential in $1D$, and there it implies a δ -function at $x = 0$ (since $\nabla^2 \psi(x) = (c_1 \delta(x) + c_2) \psi(x)$, where c_1 and c_2 are some constants), but in three dimensions it implies a somewhat milder singularity at $r = 0$ of the $1/|r|$ type (since $\nabla^2 \psi(r) = (c_1/r + c_2) \psi(r)$). The only way to get $3D$ delta function at zero is to have $\psi(r) \sim 1/r$ around zero, since $\nabla^2 1/r = 4\pi \delta^{(3)}(\vec{r})$. So the fact that with Darwin potential in $3D$ we have “irregular” solutions which diverge at zero isn't a “bug” of some sort, it's a feature!

Now back to the main line of thought; we could put the system in a gigantic “box” (sphere really) of radius L , which is much much (much) bigger than the Hydrogen atom scale a_0 ; for positive energies our regular and irregular solution at large distances behave like $\sin(\theta_l)/r$ and $\cos(\theta_l)/r$ with θ_l given by (127), so the boundary condition that the wave function vanishes at $r = L$ would produce one constraint on factors multiplying regular and irregular solution (similar as in the free case), and then integrating the Schrödinger equation around zero to get the other. But the truth is we couldn't care less about these continuum solutions, what we really care about is what happens to (existing) bound states!

And the procedure for bound states is the same: solution is the superposition of “regular” and “irregular” solution, but for some slightly different (and non-integer) n which we’ll call \bar{n} to remember it’s not really an integer; also, since we’re interested only in $l = 0$ solutions, we’ll drop the pretense that the results hold for general l . The wave function is then given by

$$\psi(r) = A_n e^{-r/(\bar{n}a_0)} {}_1F_1(1 - \bar{n}, 2, 2r/(\bar{n}a_0)) + B_n e^{-r/(\bar{n}a_0)} U(1 - \bar{n}, 2, 2r/(\bar{n}a_0)) . \quad (141)$$

At large r , the solution behaves like

$$\psi(r) = A_n \frac{e^{\frac{r}{\bar{n}a_0}}}{\Gamma(1 - \bar{n})} \left(\frac{\bar{n}a_0}{2r} \right)^{\bar{n}+1} + B_n e^{-\frac{r}{\bar{n}a_0}} \left(\frac{\bar{n}a_0}{2r} \right)^{\bar{n}-1} \quad (142)$$

and at small r like

$$\psi(r) = A_n + \frac{B_n}{\Gamma(-\bar{n})} \left(-\frac{a_0}{2r} + \log\left(\frac{r}{a_0}\right) + \log\left(\frac{2}{n}\right) + \frac{1}{2n} + 2\gamma - 1 + \psi^{(0)}(1 - n) \right) \quad (143)$$

where $\psi^{(0)}$ is the PolyGamma function

$$\psi^{(n)}(x) = \frac{\partial^{n+1}}{\partial x^{n+1}} \log \Gamma(x) \quad (144)$$

For solution to vanish at $r = L$, we have to have

$$A_n = -B_n \Gamma(1 - \bar{n}) e^{-\frac{2L}{a_0 \bar{n}}} \left(\frac{2L}{\bar{n}a_0} \right)^{2\bar{n}} \quad (145)$$

which as we can see vanishes in the $L \rightarrow \infty$ limit. To get the second boundary condition we need to integrate the Schrödinger equation around zero in a sphere of radius ϵ which we’ll then set to zero

$$\int \nabla^2 \psi(r) d^3r - 2 \frac{V_0}{m} \int \frac{1}{\pi^2} \frac{\sigma}{(r^2 + \sigma^2)^2} \psi(r) d^3r = -\frac{2}{a_0} \int \frac{\psi(r)}{|r|} d^3r + k^2 \int \psi(r) d^3r \quad (146)$$

As before, the first term get’s the only contribution from the $1/r$ term

$$\int \nabla^2 \psi(r) d^3r = -4\pi \left(-\frac{B_n a_0}{2\Gamma(-\bar{n})} \right) . \quad (147)$$

In the second term for parts independent of r we take the $\sigma \rightarrow 0$ limit first and for parts depending on r we take the $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$ limit first, to get

$$\begin{aligned} -2 \frac{V_0}{m} \int \frac{1}{\pi^2} \frac{\sigma}{(r^2 + \sigma^2)^2} \psi(r) d^3r &= -2 \frac{V_0}{m} \left\{ A_n + \frac{B_n}{\Gamma(-\bar{n})} \left(\frac{1}{2\bar{n}} + 2\gamma - 1 + \log \frac{2}{n} + \psi^{(0)}(1 - \bar{n}) \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{B_n}{\Gamma(-\bar{n})} \left(-\frac{C a_0}{2} + D \right) \right\} . \end{aligned} \quad (148)$$

where C and D are integrals of $1/r$ and $\log(r)$ parts over a sphere of radius r

$$\begin{aligned} C &= \int \delta^{(3)}(\vec{r}) \frac{1}{r} d^3r = \int_0^\epsilon \frac{1}{\pi^2} \frac{\sigma}{(r^2 + \sigma^2)^2} \frac{1}{r} 4\pi r^2 dr = \frac{2\epsilon^2}{\pi\sigma(\epsilon^2 + \sigma^2)} \\ D &= 1 + \frac{2}{\pi} \left(\log\left(\frac{\epsilon}{a}\right) \left[\arctan\left(\frac{\epsilon}{\sigma}\right) - \frac{\sigma\epsilon}{\sigma^2 + \epsilon^2} \right] - \arctan\left(\frac{\sigma}{\epsilon}\right) \right) + \frac{i}{\pi} \left(\text{Li}_2\left(\frac{i\epsilon}{\sigma}\right) - \text{Li}_2\left(-\frac{i\epsilon}{\sigma}\right) \right) \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{4n(-1 + (2n+1)\log(\epsilon/a_0))}{(2n+1)^2\pi} \left(\frac{\epsilon}{\sigma} \right)^{2n+1} \end{aligned} \quad (149)$$

where

$$\text{Li}_n(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^k}{k^n} \quad (150)$$

is the PolyLog function. Since those two terms are going to appear together, we'll call them $C \equiv Ca_0/2 - D$ for brevity.

Last two terms on the RHS vanish in the $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$ limit, and we can neglect the A_n in the $L \rightarrow \infty$ limit, so we are left with

$$2\pi a_0 - 2\frac{V_0}{m} \left(\frac{1}{2n} + 2\gamma - 1 + \log \frac{2}{n} + \psi^{(0)}(1-n) - C \right) = 0 \quad (151)$$

or

$$\left(\frac{1}{2n} + 2\gamma - 1 + \log \frac{2}{n} + \psi^{(0)}(1-n) \right)^{-1} = \frac{1}{\frac{\pi\kappa}{V_0\alpha} + C} \quad (152)$$

Left hand side of this equation is plotted in figure 2. The fact that V_0 is multiplied by α means that

Figure 2: Equation determining effective \bar{n} for Hydrogen atom with Darwin term, with levels shown for weak Darwin term (dashed line) and strong (dotted line)

Darwin corrections in Hydrogen atom will have only even powers of α . Note that $C \rightarrow \infty$ is the same as $V_0 \rightarrow 0$, which would imply that if one of those two integrals is infinite, Darwin force effects would vanish, which would be contrary to observations. Note also that the LHS vanishes for integer n , so if we

expand both sides in power series of V_0 , we can solve again term by term

$$\begin{aligned}
n_1 &= \frac{\alpha}{\pi\kappa} \\
n_1^2 \left(1 - 2\gamma - \frac{1}{2n} + \log\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) - \psi^{(0)}(n) \right) + \frac{n_2}{2} &= -\frac{\alpha^2 C}{\pi^2 \kappa^2} \\
\frac{n_3}{6} + n_1 n_2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{2n} - 2\gamma + \log\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) - \psi^{(0)}(n) \right) \\
+n_1^3 \left(\frac{3}{4n^2} - \psi^{(1)}(n) + \left(\log\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) - \psi^{(0)}(n) \right)^2 - 4\gamma^2 + \frac{\pi^2}{3} + 1 \right) \\
+ 2n_1^3 \left(1 - \frac{1}{2n} - 2\gamma \right) \left(\log\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) - \psi^{(0)}(n) - 2\gamma \right) &= \frac{\alpha^3 C^2}{\pi^3 \kappa^3} \quad (153)
\end{aligned}$$

and so on. This becomes very complicated very fast; lowest few terms are

$$\begin{aligned}
n_1 &= \frac{\alpha}{\pi\kappa} \\
n_2 &= 2\frac{\alpha^2}{\pi^2 \kappa^2} \left(\frac{1}{2n} + 2\gamma - 1 - \log\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) + \psi^{(0)}(n) - C \right) \\
n_3 &= 6\frac{\alpha^3}{\pi^3 \kappa^3} \left[\left(-\frac{1}{2n} + \log\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) - \psi^{(0)}(n) - 4\gamma \right) \left(2(C+1) - \frac{1}{2n} + \log\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) - \psi^{(0)}(n) \right) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + (1+C+2\gamma)^2 - \frac{1}{2n^2} - \frac{1}{n} - \frac{\pi^2}{3} + \psi^{(1)}(n) \right] \quad (154)
\end{aligned}$$

and so on. This yields the expression for energy

$$\begin{aligned}
E &= -\frac{m\alpha^2}{2\kappa\bar{n}^2} = -\frac{m\alpha^2}{2\kappa n^2} + \frac{m\alpha^3 V}{\pi\kappa^2 n^3} - \frac{m\alpha^4 V^2}{2\pi^2 \kappa^3 n^4} \left(\frac{1}{4n} + (1+C) - 2\gamma + \log\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) - \psi^{(0)}(n) \right) \\
&\quad - \frac{m\alpha^5 V^3}{2\pi^3 \kappa^4 n^5} \left(5 + 12n + 4\pi^2 n^2 - 12n^2 \left[\left(1 + C - 2\gamma + \log\frac{n}{2} - \psi^{(0)}(n) \right)^2 + \psi^{(1)}(n) \right] \right) \\
&\quad + \mathcal{O}(V^4) \quad (155)
\end{aligned}$$

For Darwin term in Hydrogen atom $\kappa = 1$ and $V_0 = \frac{4\pi\alpha}{8}$ yielding the energy

$$\begin{aligned}
E &= -\frac{m\alpha^2}{2n^2} + \frac{m\alpha^4}{2n^3} - \frac{m\alpha^6}{2n^3} \left(\frac{1}{4n} + (1+C) - 2\gamma + \log\frac{n}{2} - \psi^{(0)}(n) \right) \\
&\quad - \frac{m\alpha^8}{16n^3} \left(\frac{5+12n}{n^2} + 4\pi^2 - 12 \left[\left(1 + C - 2\gamma + \log\frac{n}{2} - \psi^{(0)}(n) \right)^2 + \psi^{(1)}(n) \right] \right) \quad (156)
\end{aligned}$$

Now let's compare that to perturbation theory. For Darwin potential

$$V_D = \frac{\alpha}{8m^2} 4\pi\delta^{(3)}(\vec{r}) \quad (157)$$

matrix elements between states (bound-bound, continuum-continuum and mixed) are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle n | V_D | n' \rangle &= \frac{m\alpha^4}{2(nn')^{3/2}} \cdot \\
\langle k | V_D | k' \rangle &= \frac{\bar{\alpha}}{8m^2} \frac{2k}{\sqrt{ka_0 \left(1 - e^{-\frac{2\pi}{ka_0}}\right)}} \frac{2k'}{\sqrt{k'a_0 \left(1 - e^{-\frac{2\pi}{k'a_0}}\right)}} \\
\langle n | V(r) | k' \rangle &= \frac{\bar{\alpha}}{8m^2} \frac{2}{\sqrt{n^3 a_0^3}} \frac{2k}{\sqrt{k'a_0 \left(1 - e^{-\frac{2\pi}{k'a_0}}\right)}} \quad (158)
\end{aligned}$$

First order correction is so trivial we'll skip it. Second order is given

$$E_n^{(2)} = \sum_{n' \neq n} \frac{|\langle n | V_D | n' \rangle|^2}{E_n - E_{n'}} + \int \frac{|\langle n | V_D | k \rangle|^2}{E_n - E_k} dk \quad (159)$$

First term collects contributions from other bound states and is given by

$$\sum_{n' \neq n} \frac{|\langle n | V_D | n' \rangle|^2}{E_n - E_{n'}} = \frac{m\alpha^6}{2n^3} \sum_{n' \neq n} \frac{1}{n'^3 \left(\frac{1}{n^2} - \frac{1}{n'^2}\right)} = -\frac{m\alpha^6}{2n^3} \left(\frac{1}{4n} - \gamma - \psi^{(0)}(n)\right) \quad (160)$$

Second term diverges, but if our general formula is correct, then we can see that only for all but ground state contribution from continuum states is actually bigger than contribution from bound states.

5 Hydrogen atom with Darwin potential in momentum space

Let's repeat this in momentum space; for evaluating wave function (141) in momentum space, we'll need integrals

$$\int_0^\infty e^{-\lambda z} z^\nu {}_1F_1(\alpha, \gamma, 2kz) dz = \frac{\Gamma(1+\nu)}{\lambda^{1+\nu}} {}_2F_1(\alpha, 1+\nu, \gamma, 2k/\lambda) \quad (161)$$

$$\int_0^\infty e^{-\lambda z} z^\nu U(\alpha, \gamma, 2kz) dz = \frac{\Gamma(1+\nu)}{\lambda^{1+\nu}} \frac{\Gamma(\gamma-\alpha)}{\Gamma(\gamma)} {}_2F_1(\alpha, 1+\nu, \alpha+2+\nu-\gamma, 1-2k/\lambda) \quad (162)$$

where values of parameters are such that integrals converge (so $\Re\lambda > 0$, γ not a negative integer, and so on). In general we would use the formula

$$e^{i\vec{q}\cdot\vec{r}} = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} i^\ell j_\ell(qr) 4\pi \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} Y_{\ell m}^*(\hat{q}) Y_{\ell m}(\hat{r}) \quad (163)$$

to expand $e^{i\vec{q}\cdot\vec{r}}$ in spherical harmonics, but since we're only interested in $\ell = 0$ case, we can just set the vector \vec{r} to point along the \hat{z} axis and integrate over angles. Let's look at plain hydrogen first; wave

function is then

$$\begin{aligned}
\psi(q) &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \int e^{iqr \cos \theta} e^{-kr} {}_1F_1(1-n, 2, 2kr) 2\pi r^2 d \cos \theta dr \\
&= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{1/2}} \int \frac{e^{iqr} - e^{-iqr}}{iqr} e^{-kr} {}_1F_1(1-n, 2, 2kr) r^2 dr \\
&= \frac{\Gamma(2)}{\sqrt{2\pi} iq} \left(\frac{{}_2F_1\left(1-n, 2, 2, \frac{2k}{k-iq}\right)}{(k-iq)^2} - \frac{{}_2F_1\left(1-n, 2, 2, \frac{2k}{k+iq}\right)}{(k+iq)^2} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{164}$$

where $k = 1/(na_0)$ for bound states (with n integer). This is clearly a real function, and since

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z} {}_2F_1(a, b, c, z) = \frac{ab}{c} {}_2F_1(a+1, b+1, c+1, z) \tag{165}$$

we can write it as a real part of total derivative (dropping irrelevant constants)

$$\psi(q) = \frac{\partial}{\partial q^2} \left[{}_2F_1\left(-n, 1, 1, \frac{2k}{k+iq}\right) + {}_2F_1\left(-n, 1, 1, \frac{2k}{k-iq}\right) \right] = \frac{\partial}{\partial q^2} \Re[F(q)] = \frac{1}{2q} \frac{\partial}{\partial q} \Re[F(q)] \tag{166}$$

with

$$F(q) = {}_2F_1\left(-n, 1, 1, \frac{2k}{k-iq}\right) = \left(\frac{-k-iq}{k-iq}\right)^n \tag{167}$$

where in the last step we used the fact that (for any γ)

$${}_2F_1(\alpha, \gamma, \gamma, z) = (1-z)^{-\alpha}. \tag{168}$$

Now, Schrödinger equation in momentum space

$$\frac{p^2}{2m} \psi(p) - \frac{e^2}{(2\pi)^3} \int \frac{1}{(\vec{p}-\vec{q})^2 + \mu^2} \psi(q) d^3q = E\psi(q) \tag{169}$$

after multiplying with $2m$ and moving some terms around becomes

$$\left(p^2 + \frac{1}{n^2 a_0^2}\right) \psi(p) = \frac{1}{\pi^2 a_0} \int \frac{1}{(\vec{p}-\vec{q})^2 + \mu^2} \psi(q) d^3q. \tag{170}$$

To evaluate the integral on the RHS, we'd again have to expand $[(\vec{p}-\vec{q})^2 + \mu^2]^{-1}$ into spherical harmonics, but since again we're looking at $l = 0$ solution, we again can set \vec{p} to point along z -axis and integrate over angles

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{1}{\pi^2 a_0} \int \frac{1}{(\vec{p}-\vec{q})^2 + \mu^2} \psi(q) 2\pi d \cos \theta q^2 dq &= \frac{1}{\pi a_0} \int_0^\infty \frac{\log \frac{(p+q)^2 + \mu^2}{(p-q)^2 + \mu^2}}{pq} \psi(q) q^2 dq \\
&= \frac{1}{2\pi a_0 p} \int_0^\infty \log \frac{(p+q)^2 + \mu^2}{(p-q)^2 + \mu^2} \psi(q) 2q dq.
\end{aligned} \tag{171}$$

We can now use partial integration (with $\psi(q) = \Re[\partial F(q)/\partial q^2]$), to get

$$\left(p^2 + \frac{1}{n^2 a_0^2}\right) \frac{\partial \Re F(p)}{\partial p^2} = -\frac{1}{2\pi a_0 p} \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{(p+q)}{(p+q)^2 + \mu^2} + \frac{(p-q)}{(p-q)^2 + \mu^2} \right) \Re[F(q)] dq. \tag{172}$$

Since $\Re[F(q)] = F(q) + F^*(q)$ is an even function of q , we can extend the integration to $-\infty$,

$$\left(p^2 + \frac{1}{n^2 a_0^2}\right) \frac{\partial(F(p) + F^*(p))}{\partial p^2} = -\frac{1}{2\pi a_0 p} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(p+q)}{(p+q)^2 + \mu^2} + \frac{(p-q)}{(p-q)^2 + \mu^2} \right) (F(q) + F^*(q)) dq .$$

Now, since $F(q)$ has no poles in the upper half of complex plane, we can use residue theorem to evaluate the integral, using

$$\text{Res}_{q \rightarrow p \pm i\mu} \frac{(p-q)}{(p-q)^2 + \mu^2} = -1 , \quad \text{Res}_{q \rightarrow -p \pm i\mu} \frac{(p+q)}{(p+q)^2 + \mu^2} = 1 , \quad (173)$$

and then setting $\mu \rightarrow 0$; similarly, $F^*(q)$ has no poles in the lower half of the complex plane, so we can use the residue theorem by closing the loop in the lower half (which produces an extra minus sign, since the loop integral now is in the opposite direction), to get

$$\begin{aligned} \left(p^2 + \frac{1}{n^2 a_0^2}\right) \frac{\partial(F(p) + F^*(p))}{\partial p^2} &= \frac{1}{4\pi a_0 p} 2\pi i (F(p) - F(-p) - (F^*(p) - F^*(-p))) \\ &= \frac{i}{a_0 p} (F(p) - F^*(p)) \end{aligned} \quad (174)$$

where last line comes from $F(-p) = F^*(p)$. This is still a fully real equation, but we can replace it with complex differential equation

$$\frac{1}{2p} \left[\left(p^2 + \frac{1}{n^2 a_0^2}\right) F'(p) + \frac{2i}{a_0} F(p) \right] = 0 \quad (175)$$

which it's trivial to show that it holds for (167). What happens if when we add Darwin potential? Wave function is now

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(q) &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \int e^{iqr \cos \theta} e^{-kr} U(1 - \bar{n}, 2, 2kr) 2\pi r^2 d \cos \theta dr \\ &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{1/2}} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{iqr} - e^{-iqr}}{iqr} e^{-kr} U(1 - \bar{n}, 2, 2kr) r^2 dr \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \left(\frac{{}_2\tilde{F}_1\left(1 - \bar{n}, 2, 2 - \bar{n}, 1 - \frac{2k}{k-iq}\right)}{iq(k-iq)^2} - \frac{{}_2\tilde{F}_1\left(1 - \bar{n}, 2, 2 - \bar{n}, 1 - \frac{2k}{k+iq}\right)}{iq(k+iq)^2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (176)$$

where $k = 1/(\bar{n}a_0)$ for bound states, but \bar{n} is no longer integer, and

$${}_2\tilde{F}_1(a, b, c, z) = \frac{{}_2F_1(a, b, c, z)}{\Gamma(c)} \quad (177)$$

is regularized hypergeometric function. This is again clearly a real function, and as before we can write

$$\psi(q) = \frac{\partial}{\partial q^2} \Re[F(q)] \quad \text{with} \quad F(q) = \frac{\mathcal{N}_n}{\sqrt{2\pi}\Gamma(2 - \bar{n})} {}_2F_1\left(-\bar{n}, 1, 1 - \bar{n}, 1 - \frac{2k}{k-iq}\right) \quad (178)$$

where \mathcal{N}_n is the normalization constant (135) and which we'll drop for brevity. Schrödinger equation in momentum space is now

$$\frac{p^2}{2m} \psi(p) - \frac{e^2}{(2\pi)^3} \int \frac{1}{(\vec{p} - \vec{q})^2 + \mu^2} \psi(q) d^3q - E\psi(p) = -\frac{V_0/m^2}{(2\pi)^3} \int \frac{(\vec{p} - \vec{q})^2}{(\vec{p} - \vec{q})^2 + \mu^2} \psi(q) d^3q \quad (179)$$

which after multiplying with $2m$ and moving some terms around becomes

$$\left(p^2 + \frac{1}{\bar{n}^2 a_0^2}\right) \psi(p) - \int \left\{ \frac{\frac{1}{\pi^2 a_0} - \mu^2 \frac{2V_0/m}{(2\pi)^3}}{(\vec{p}-\vec{q})^2 + \mu^2} \right\} \psi(q) d^3q = -\frac{2V_0/m}{(2\pi)^3} \int \psi(q) d^3q. \quad (180)$$

In the first integral (on the LHS) we can drop the μ^2 part in the numerator since we'll be taking $\mu \rightarrow 0$ limit anyway. What's left on LHS is then essentially the Schrödinger equation for hydrogen, so evaluating it goes along the exact same lines (but with different $F(q)$), yielding

$$\left(p^2 + \frac{1}{\bar{n}^2 a_0^2}\right) \frac{\partial(F(p) + F^*(p))}{\partial p^2} + \frac{1}{2\pi a_0 p} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(p+q)}{(p+q)^2 + \mu^2} + \frac{(p-q)}{(p-q)^2 + \mu^2} \right) (F(q) + F^*(q)) dq.$$

Since the hypergeometric function ${}_2F_1(a, b, c, z)$ has a branch line from $z = 1$ to ∞ , $F(q)$ has a branch line from $q \in \langle -\infty i, -i/n \rangle$ and $F^*(q)$ from $q \in [i/n, i\infty)$; so in both cases we can use the residue theorem (like in plain Hydrogen case) and the contribution from the four poles at $q = \pm p \pm i\mu$ yields

$$LHS = \frac{1}{2p} \left\{ \left(p^2 + \frac{1}{\bar{n}^2 a_0^2}\right) (F'(p) + F^{*'}(p)) + \frac{2i}{a_0} (F(p) - F^*(p)) \right\} = -\bar{n} \quad (181)$$

which is a constant, which is encouraging, since the RHS of (180) is clearly also a constant. To evaluate that RHS, remember that in the derivation of (59) we added a small imaginary part to r to make the integrals converge; that small imaginary part is $e^{-k\sigma}$, so formula (60) is really a Fourier transform of momentum space potential

$$V(\vec{p}-\vec{q}) = \lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \frac{V_0/m^2}{(2\pi)^3} e^{-\sigma|\vec{p}-\vec{q}|}. \quad (182)$$

Since $|\vec{p}-\vec{q}| = E_{\vec{p}-\vec{q}}$ is the energy of the exchanged photon, we'll also add a small mass μ to it $E_{\vec{p}-\vec{q}} = \sqrt{(\vec{p}-\vec{q})^2 + \mu^2}$ to move those poles away from the real axis; this yields

$$V(\vec{p}-\vec{q}) = \lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \frac{V_0/m^2}{(2\pi)^3} e^{-\sigma E_{\vec{p}-\vec{q}}} = \lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \frac{V_0/m^2}{(2\pi)^3} e^{-\sigma \sqrt{(\vec{p}-\vec{q})^2 + \mu^2}}. \quad (183)$$

RHS of (180) then becomes

$$RHS = -\frac{2V_0/m}{(2\pi)^3} \int e^{-\sigma E_{\vec{p}-\vec{q}}} \psi(q) d^3q = -\frac{2V_0/m}{(2\pi)^2} \int e^{-\sigma \sqrt{p^2+q^2-2pq \cos \theta + \mu^2}} \psi(q) q^2 d \cos \theta dq \quad (184)$$

Integral over angle θ yields

$$\int_{-1}^1 e^{-\sigma \sqrt{p^2+q^2-2pq \cos \theta + \mu^2}} d \cos \theta = \frac{f(p, q)}{pq} \quad (185)$$

with

$$f(p, q) = \frac{e^{-\sigma E_{p-q}} (1 + \sigma E_{p-q}) - e^{-\sigma E_{p+q}} (1 + \sigma E_{p+q})}{\sigma^2} \quad (186)$$

After substituting $\psi(q) = \partial \Re[F(q)] / \partial q^2$, equation (184) can then be partially integrated

$$\begin{aligned} RHS &= -\frac{2V_0/m}{p(2\pi)^2} \int f(p, q) \psi(q) q dq = -\frac{2V_0/m}{2p(2\pi)^2} \int f(p, q) \frac{\partial \Re[F(q)]}{\partial q} dq \\ &= -\frac{2V_0/m}{2p(2\pi)^2} \left[f(p, q) * \Re[F(q)] \Big|_0^\infty - \int \frac{\partial f(p, q)}{\partial q} \Re[F(q)] dq \right] \end{aligned} \quad (187)$$

with

$$\frac{\partial f(p, q)}{\partial q} = ((p - q)e^{-\sigma E_{p-q}} + (p + q)e^{-\sigma E_{p+q}}) \quad (188)$$

Now, this is the key point here. For *any finite* σ , first term vanishes because $f(p, q)$ vanishes at both $q = 0$ and $q = \infty$, so we are left with

$$RHS = \frac{2V_0/m}{2p(2\pi)^2} \left[\int_0^\infty ((p - q)e^{-\sigma E_{p-q}} + (p + q)e^{-\sigma E_{p+q}}) \Re[F(q)] dq \right] \quad (189)$$

but if we had let $\sigma \rightarrow 0$ first, then we'd have

$$\lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} f(p, q) = 2pq + \mathcal{O}(\sigma) \quad (190)$$

which cancels with $2p$ in the denominator to yield q , so the first term in partial integration becomes $q\Re[F(q)]|_0^\infty$ which is infinite. This yields the same result as if we had simply tried to integrate $\psi(q)q^2 dq = \partial\Re[F(q)]/\partial q^2 * q^2 dq$ by parts; our regularization removes this infinity, and it's analogous to our claim that in coordinate space we should take the $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$ limit before $\sigma \rightarrow 0$ limit when we calculate integral of $\delta^{(3)}(\vec{r}) * 1/r$.

Anyway, if we accept that this is the correct procedure (which it may or may not be), then in the equation (189) we can now take the $\sigma \rightarrow 0$ limit, where

$$\lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} ((p - q)e^{-\sigma E_{p-q}} + (p + q)e^{-\sigma E_{p+q}}) = 2p + \mathcal{O}(\sigma) \quad (191)$$

so the RHS becomes

$$RHS = \frac{2V_0/m}{(2\pi)^2} \int_0^\infty (F(q) + F^*(q)) dq \quad (192)$$

which is even, so we can extend the integration to $-\infty$ and then evaluate using the residue theorem. Since $F(q)$ doesn't have any poles in the upper half of the plane, and $F^*(q)$ doesn't have any poles in the lower half, we'll close the loop in upper/lower half respectively. Loop integrals yield zero (since there are no poles there now), so the integral from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$ has to be equal to the sum of two integrals over loops of radius Q (which we will set to infinity afterwards). In the upper plane we'll parametrize the semi-circle as $q = Qe^{i\phi}$ and in the lower plane it will be $q = Qe^{-i\phi}$ so in both cases integral over semi-circle becomes an integral over ϕ from 0 to π . To evaluate them, we need to expand hypergeometric function around infinity:

$$\begin{aligned} {}_2F_1\left(-\bar{n}, 1, 1 - \bar{n}, 1 - \frac{2}{\bar{n}a_0}\right) &= \bar{n} \left(\gamma + \psi^{(0)}(-n) + \log\left(\frac{2}{\bar{n}}\right) \right) - \bar{n} \log(\mp iqa_0) \left(1 \mp \frac{2i}{qa_0} \right) \\ &\mp \frac{2i\bar{n} \left(\frac{1}{2\bar{n}} + \gamma - 1 + \log\left(\frac{2}{\bar{n}}\right) + \psi^{(0)}(1 - \bar{n}) \right)}{qa_0} + \mathcal{O}(q^{-2}). \end{aligned} \quad (193)$$

First (constant) term when integrated over the arc becomes

$$\int_C dq = \int_0^\phi (\pm i)Qe^{\pm i\phi} d\phi = -2Q \quad (194)$$

so contributions from $F(q)$ and $F^*(q)$ cancel out due to that extra minus one factor because first loop integral is in counter-clockwise direction and second in clockwise. Second (logarithmic) term is

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_C \bar{n} \log(\mp iq) \left(1 \mp \frac{2i}{q}\right) dq &= \int_0^\pi \bar{n} \log(e^{\mp i\pi/2} Q e^{\pm i\phi}) \left(1 \mp \frac{2i}{Q e^{\pm i\phi}}\right) Q e^{\pm i\phi} (\pm i) d\phi \\
&= \pm i \bar{n} \int_0^\pi (\log(Q) \pm i(\phi - \pi/2))(Q e^{i\phi} \mp 2i) d\phi \\
&= 2\bar{n}(Q + (\pi - Q) \log(Q))
\end{aligned} \tag{195}$$

so these terms again cancel (for the same reason). Third term with $1/q$ dependence becomes

$$\int_C \frac{1}{q} dq = (\pm i) \int_0^\pi \frac{1}{Q e^{\pm i\phi}} Q e^{\pm i\phi} d\phi = \pm i\pi \tag{196}$$

so it's the only term that contributes in $Q \rightarrow \infty$ limit, since all other terms behave as $1/Q^n$ with $n > 0$ and vanish. The result is then

$$RHS = -\frac{V_0 \bar{n}}{\pi m a_0} \left(\frac{1}{2\bar{n}} + \gamma - 1 + \log\left(\frac{2}{\bar{n}}\right) + \psi^{(0)}(1 - \bar{n}) \right) \tag{197}$$

which when combined with LHS leads to condition

$$1 = \frac{V_0 \alpha}{\pi \kappa} \left(\frac{1}{2\bar{n}} + \gamma - 1 + \log\left(\frac{2}{\bar{n}}\right) + \psi^{(0)}(1 - \bar{n}) \right) \tag{198}$$

which is the same as (152) with $C = 0$. This obviously depends (at least somewhat) on our choice of using $\lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} e^{-\sigma|\vec{p}-\vec{q}|}$ in momentum space to regularize the potential energy (which leads to $\delta^{(3)}(\vec{r}) \rightarrow \sigma/(r^2 + \sigma^2)^2$ in coordinate space), so what should that regularization function look like? First thing to notice is that the final result doesn't depend on p , so we could have used $e^{-\sigma q}$ instead of $e^{-\sigma|\vec{p}-\vec{q}|}$ and the final result would have been the same. We didn't because potential $V(\vec{p}, \vec{q})$ has to be a function only of momentum difference $V(\vec{p} - \vec{q})$ to give us local potential in coordinate space, but in this particular example it doesn't matter.

One thing we can hopefully all agree on is that the source of all the problems is the behavior of the potential for large p in momentum space; any potential that doesn't vanish at infinity will produce a δ -function in coordinate space, so our "regularization" has to vanish as $q \rightarrow \infty$. On the other hand, we don't want it to modify the potential at finite momenta, or otherwise it's going to produce a fundamentally different system, so what we need is something that's equal to 1 for small momenta, and vanishes at large momenta, which sounds exactly like a momentum cutoff $Q = 1/\sigma$ at some large momentum or

$$V(\vec{p} - \vec{q}) = \theta(Q - |\vec{p} - \vec{q}|) \tag{199}$$

but we want smooth version of it to avoid having to deal with the delta function in the derivative, so something like

$$V(\vec{p} - \vec{q}) = \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\frac{2}{\pi} \arctan\left(\lambda \left(\frac{1}{\sigma} - (\vec{p} - \vec{q})^2\right)\right)}{2} \tag{200}$$

which becomes Heaviside theta function in the limit $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$. For simplicity we can set $\lambda = 1/\sigma$ so that we have to deal with only one limit, but we don't have to. We'll leave it as an exercise to the reader to show (200) with either $\vec{p} - \vec{q}$ or just \vec{q} leads to the same result as we derived.

Now, the question that remains is if there are regularization schemes where the term in partial integration $f(p, q)\Re[F(q)]|_0^\infty$ will produce a non-zero contribution (that's equivalent to having finite C in equation (152))? It would be nice if someone⁹ could derive some sort of formal theory of what kind of regularization is acceptable here and what isn't; we'll just take it on good faith that the ones we used are.

6 Summary and conclusion

To paraphrase Jim Morrison, "This is the end, beautiful friend". We have derived an exact solution for Hydrogen atom with Darwin potential in coordinate and momentum space; that solution may or may not be correct, since it depends on "regularizing" the Darwin potential.

On the plus side, our result does seem to agree with the first order perturbation theory results (which doesn't really prove anything), and our regularization scheme seems to make sense to us, but on the minus side, we don't know how to prove that all other regularization schemes (which may lead to different result) are not valid.

It would be nice if we could compare the results to some observed experimental values (preferably for multiple values of V_0) that go beyond the first order perturbation theory, but we don't know of any (if you do, please @ us!).

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⁹"A mathematician! A mathematician! My kingdom for a mathematician!", to paraphrase Billy